

Challenges In Teaching English Speech Sounds To Non-Native Speakers Using British Dictionaries

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Abstract: *Naturally, a speaker's misproduction of speech sounds not only reaches but disorients the listener. If the listener has to struggle to understand the construct, they might miss the message—leaving the speaker's intended impact lost. Every speaker aims to achieve the objective of their speech, which drives the need to communicate effectively and seek learning. For every learner, there is a teacher. Thus, this study sought to examine how British dictionaries assist non-native learners in mastering English speech sounds, analyze these dictionaries' effectiveness in helping non-native speakers acquire accurate pronunciation, and identify the specific challenges non-native speakers face when using the dictionaries. Framed in Sweller's (1988) Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) and Lado's (1957) Contrastive Analysis Theory (CAT), the study used a comparative qualitative research design to analyze 27 screenshots from six notable British dictionaries, categorized into six themes. Findings revealed ways various British dictionaries present phonemic transcriptions, the inclusion of new phonemes in their vowel systems, and their approaches to marking prosody. It was also found that formatting is disrupted in some (of the) dictionaries, and there are instances of non-correspondence between offline mobile and online versions. The researcher concludes that dictionaries serve different lexicographic purposes and target specific users, so some lexicographic features are pedagogically intentional rather than errors. Teachers are advised to recognize this and review dictionary contents to determine which to use and how. The researcher recommends that dictionary makers maintain consistency in lexicographic entries to reduce cognitive load on both teachers and learners.*

Keywords: British Dictionaries, English, Speech Sounds, Teaching, Learning, Challenges

INTRODUCTION

English remains the language of choice for many in the 21st century, maintaining its position as the most spoken second language and the second most spoken first language. Crystal (2003, p. 26) notes that “English is now so widely established that it can no longer be thought of as ‘owned’ by any single nation”. Its global appeal has led speakers of other languages to adopt it, prompting non-English-speaking communities to use it as their lingua franca, official, or national language. Plonski et al. (2013, p. 1) reveal that Rwanda, once a French-speaking country, made English an official language—a move also taken by Burundi and Gabon, while South Sudan also adopted English. Assan and Walker (2018) confirm that Rwanda, which had French as its colonial language, switched to English in late 2008. Additionally, Crystal (2003, p. 5) states that “in 1996... English replaced French as the chief foreign language in schools in Algeria (a former French colony)”.

English dominates global media, the internet, entertainment, and international communication and conferences—where, as Cruttenden (2014, p. 6) puts it, “the common language is almost always English even in situations where none of the participants is a native speaker of English”—making proficiency in it highly sought after. As a result, learners focus on all four language skills—speaking, writing, reading, and listening—with speaking often taking priority. Communicators tend to favour verbal interaction over writing and its formalities, as clear speech, even with some expertise, ensures quicker understanding. Reid (2016, p. 19) asserts, “correct pronunciation is without doubt a fundamental feature of successful communication in the English language”. Spoken proficiency begins with speech sound production, advancing to word formation with proper stress and aspiration. According to Carley et al. (2018, p. 35), “the learner has to work out the phonemic inventory of the new language and all the phonetic variants”. Beyond pronunciation, grammar plays a key role in reading or speaking, with intonation, rhythm, and other elements enhancing meaning. These stages—sound production, word formation, pronunciation, and sentence structuring—are facilitated by dictionaries, which serve as learning tools, allowing students to study independently with minimal guidance. As such, dictionaries are vital to learning spoken English.

Correct pronunciation is a challenge for many non-native speakers, primarily due to inadequate early exposure. Reid (2016, p. 19) advises that “attention should be paid to teaching pronunciation right from the beginning of English language teaching”. Many communities, particularly non-native ones, overlook correct pronunciation. For example, the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) only introduced an Oral English test in 1995, even though English had been spoken in West

African countries for over a century. Ogunbekun (2023) also confirms that Nigeria's National Primary Schools Curriculum was updated in 2013 to incorporate "Phonetics into the curriculum in English Studies".

Without proper guidance during language acquisition, children struggle to master English speech sounds, carrying these challenges into later stages of learning. This often results from a lack of resources, unqualified teachers, and weak language environments. With these obstacles in mind, this study examines the role of dictionaries in learning English speech sounds. While dictionaries assist with word meanings, pronunciation, and usage, their varying content can complicate English learning. Yoshida (2013, p. 177) observes, "the English spelling system does not have a good reputation. In fact, most learners probably think it's a hopeless mess".

This study specifically investigates how dictionaries—particularly popular British ones—affect learning English speech sounds, whether used independently or under a tutor's guidance. While assessing how British dictionaries impact teaching English speech sounds to non-native speakers, it is the objective of this study to:

- i. Examine how British dictionaries present phonetic transcriptions and pronunciation guidance for non-native learners.
- ii. Analyze the effectiveness of British dictionaries in helping non-native speakers acquire accurate English pronunciation.
- iii. Identify the specific challenges non-native English speakers face when learning speech sounds using British dictionaries.

This study is valuable to teachers struggling to understand why apparently serious English learners still perform poorly in real-world spoken English use and exams. It guides Phonology teachers in using major British dictionaries effectively without complicating language learning. The transcription schemes of the investigated dictionaries will be unveiled to the teachers and learners unfamiliar with their objectives and content as guides to English speech sound learning. Addressing a research gap, this is the first comprehensive examination of the authoritativeness of selected dictionaries, discussed collectively. Its findings will help learners and teachers maximize these dictionaries' benefits rather than view them as unhelpful.

This study primarily examines the impact of select British dictionaries on learning English speech sounds by analyzing their phonological representations. Only mobile digital and online versions are considered, as they are the most recently updated — this might be in line with Lewis and Mees' (2017, p. 353) prediction that "in the not very distant future it is probable that paper dictionaries will be found only in libraries if not only in museums". The focus is on the graphic representation of pronunciation, excluding other speech sound investigation methods. Recorded pronunciations and text-to-speech synthesis are not included. The study is mainly for non-native English speakers and secondarily for curious natives unaware of these dictionaries' impact on non-natives learning English speech sounds.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In addressing the research questions and achieving the stated objectives, this study is informed by the four key concepts outlined below.

The Pedagogical Role of Dictionaries in Speech Sound Proficiency

Writing is a medium of communication where every writer has a message, an aim, and an audience. Even personal notes never meant for others still have the writer as their audience. Writing seeks to tell or show—whether to persuade, inform, or entertain—aligning with what instructors do. Dictionaries, as written works, follow this principle. Since early lexicography, when linguists undertook dictionary publication, to the present, where scholars debate lexicography's independence from linguistics, the best or most popular dictionaries consider user type and learning needs. Language users at various proficiency levels consult dictionaries for spelling, usage, pronunciation, and more. Dictionaries meeting these needs are widely accepted and recommended.

Dictionaries serve learners at different proficiency levels—beginner, intermediate, and advanced. According to Gous (2010, p. 55), identifying dictionary users determines its functions and structure. At the beginner level, learners, whether juvenile or adult, use dictionaries to understand word meanings. At this stage, children are gifted dictionaries, and recommendations to get some are made for adults. Speech sounds are best taught with visual and audio aids while focus remains on accurate sound production. As Carley et al. (2018, p. 35) note, "your first task is to make sure you never lose a phoneme contrast". Saleh and Akoshi (2023, p. 7) also recommend sound-letter patterns which learners find interesting.

At the intermediate level, learners with now expanded vocabularies grasp additional dictionary features like phonetic transcriptions, synonyms, antonyms, homophones, and word usage. This typically begins in later primary education, though individual progress varies. Learners at this stage are also familiar with pronunciation respelling, which guides them through phonemic transcriptions. After mastering phonemes at the beginner level, they focus on pronunciation and the application of segmental and suprasegmental features of spoken English and transcribed English sounds. Fast learners could use their dictionaries independently.

At the advanced level, where most learners near the end of secondary education, they refine pronunciation considering prosodic features such as intonation, speed, and rhythm. They use dictionaries with the aim to attain native speaker proficiency, creating and identifying phonetic transcriptions of English expressions. Some of these learners acquire dictionaries designed for native speakers, in their insatiable hunger to learn more; thus, emphasizing the significance of Contrastive Analysis which

according to Al-khresheh (2016, p. 336) is “a complementary and necessary part of the theory of SLA, one that cannot be ignored”.

This study aims keenly at the advanced and, to some extent, intermediate stages of learning English speech sounds for non-natives. At these levels, learners engage deeply with dictionaries to meet their needs. Some learners, particularly inquisitive or studious, acquire multiple advanced dictionaries for comparison. Following this, Yoshida (2013, p. 60) states that learners “need plenty of practice with language in realistic contexts to master its use, and the same is true about teaching pronunciation”. It is important to note that the reputation of dictionaries and scholarly reviews influence users to combine different dictionaries for a more effective learning experience. Since no dictionary satisfies every lexicographic need, learners use multiple sources for a comprehensive understanding.

Dictionaries must effectively enlighten students; otherwise, they lose their value. Kelly (2000, p. 11) also notes that “a consideration of learners' pronunciation errors and how these can inhibit successful communication is a useful basis on which to assess why it is important to deal with pronunciation in the classroom”. Teaching and learning speech sounds is particularly challenging for non-native speakers. As Reid (2016, p. 19) notes, “it is quite common to assimilate English sounds to the mother tongue sounds and to apply other suprasegmental features of the native language to pronunciation of English”. Consequently, Gous (2010, p. 56) advises that “the lexicographer should realise that the specific dictionary has a pedagogical assignment. The presentation and treatment should be done accordingly”.

Dictionaries are essential for teaching speech sounds to non-native speakers, which is why they include phonetic representations—something native speakers may not need. Modern digital dictionaries further support learning by offering spoken features for pronunciation practice. This allows both underprepared phonics tutors and students to improve by studying phonetic transcriptions through various dictionary tools. While scholars like Sustarsic (2005, p. 88) argue that “sounds and letters in English simply don't agree”, Yoshida (2013, p. 177) maintains that most English words do follow regular spelling-sound patterns, even if they can sometimes be complex. Kelly (2000, p. 123) reinforces this, noting that “English spelling is not as irregular as it seems”, with research showing that 80% of words adhere to consistent spelling rules. To ensure effective instruction, teachers should master pronunciation and transcription, especially for words with irregular grapheme-phoneme relationships.

Dictionaries play a key role in teaching accurate pronunciation and other language skills, making them reliable reference tools. Atkins and Rundell (2008, p. 45) note that dictionaries’ “generalizations about word behaviour approximate closely to the ways in which people normally use (and understand) language when engaging in real communicative acts”. The said people are native speakers. Dictionaries help uncover word properties that a teacher may not have learned from a native speaker or that a student may have misheard from a teacher. For instance, they show that ‘key’ and ‘quay’ are pronounced the same, ‘ewe’ sounds like ‘you’, and ‘suite’ rhymes with ‘sweet’, not ‘suit’. They also clarify words with identical spellings but different pronunciations, like ‘bow’ (rhyming with ‘sow’) and ‘bow’ (rhyming with ‘cow’). Phonetic transcription makes a word’s internal sound properties visible, helping learners connect sounds to spelling. It can even be more useful than spoken features, as Yoshida (2013, p. 17) points out: “Recorded words slip by quickly, and their sounds can be hard to catch, especially if the sound quality from tiny speakers is not clear, if there’s background noise, or if the user of the device must keep the volume turned low to avoid disturbing others”.

The Evolution of English Pronunciation and Lexicography

The English language has never had a regulatory body to standardize its usage, unlike French, which has the Académie Française, and Spanish, which has the Real Academia Española. Yet, despite external influences and lexical contributions from other languages, English has maintained unique linguistic peculiarities. Scholars and lexicographers like Kenrick (1773) and Johnson (1755) have attempted to determine what constitutes English vocabulary. While some proposals were accepted, others were dismissed. Justifying the need for standardization, Johnson (1747, p. 2) notes, “I had read indeed of times... in which dictionaries were written under the protection of greatness”. Emphasizing the importance of preserving pronunciation, he further asserts, “closely connected with orthography is Pronunciation, the stability of which is of great importance to the duration of a language” (p. 22).

Before and after Johnson, scholars sought to document English pronunciation in dictionaries. Lewis and Mees (2017, p. 334) note that Bailey (1727), in guiding users on pronunciation, was the first “to indicate with full regularity the positions of tonic stresses in all words,” while Kenrick (1773), imitating Bailey’s stress marking, was “the first ever to supply full pronunciations for practically all his entries”. These early efforts by educated native speakers aimed to guide both less-educated users and the few foreign enthusiasts in correctly using English. Despite extensive lexical borrowing, English has retained its distinctiveness. Its history has shaped it into a flexible, evolving language. Crystal (2003, p. 2) observes, “nobody owns it any more... everyone who has learned it now owns it”.

Before the 16th century, lexicographers did not include pronunciation guides, though some scholars examined the relationship between English letters and sounds. Continuing efforts to refine pronunciation representation, Murray (1884) introduced raised dots for stress marking instead of Bailey and Kenrick’s vertical strokes, as in ‘a·bov’ instead of ‘a'bov’, for ‘above’. Lewis and Mees (2017) confirm that this system remained in use in the Oxford English Dictionary until 1989, when it was replaced by the phonetic notation developed by the International Phonetic Association (IPA). The global status of English

validates its tumultuous history, as now everybody wants to speak English. In Crystal's (2003, p. xiii) ideal world, "everyone would have fluent command of a single world language".

As Barber et al. (2009, p. 245) note, "speakers often vary their speech according to the social context and the effect they wish to have". To standardize pronunciation, the International Phonetic Association introduced a phonetic alphabet. Otto Jespersen initially suggested the idea to Paul Passy, a French linguist, who led the association's formation in 1886 (formally named in 1897). The IPA was designed to represent spoken sounds in writing. According to the IPA (1999, p. 3), "it is desirable to have a consistent way of representing the sounds of language in written form". Crystal (2010, p. 166) states its key principles: "there should be a separate letter for each distinctive sound, and that the same symbol should be used for that sound in any language in which it appears". Though "modified and extended several times" (Crystal, 2010, p. 166), the IPA was widely accepted for its simplicity and comprehensiveness. The IPA (1999, p. 195) notes, "the choice of symbols was dictated by the need to keep them as simple as possible, for the benefit of both teachers and school children". Yoshida (2013, p. 176) acknowledges its utility: "written symbols are more permanent than sounds. We can take our time to look at them, think about them, and try to say them to ourselves".

The IPA's effectiveness is evident in the success of the Jones (1917)'s *The English Pronouncing Dictionary* (EPD), the first English dictionary to use the IPA for phonetic transcription. Lewis and Mees (2017, p. 348) describe it as "an instant and lasting success". Wells (2000, p. vii) affirms, "EPD has set the standard against which other dictionaries must inevitably be judged". Major English dictionaries have since adopted the IPA for pronunciation transcription, solidifying its role in linguistic documentation.

Pronunciation Models in British Dictionaries

According to Cruttenden (2014, p. 4), "a standard pronunciation has been evolving at least since the invention of printing in the fifteenth century... Since then the direction of change has been towards dilution of what was called RP". Unlike other English dictionaries that predominantly use the pronunciation respelling system, British English dictionaries transcribe pronunciation using the IPA. This applies to both native-oriented dictionaries and those designed for learners. Emphasizing that American dictionaries differ due to the American preference for transcribing phones with orthography, Sustarsic (2005, p. 88) notes that such authors "in order to compensate for the lack of a sufficient number of letters... make use of various digraphs and diacritics". Barber et al. (2009, p. 248) also observe that "the speech of the vast majority of Americans and Canadians, however, is rhotic, and one consequence of this is that the centring diphthongs /ɪə/, /eə/ and /ʊə/ do not exist in their system".

According to the IPA (1999, p. 159), the alphabet is "intended to be a set of symbols for representing all the possible sounds of the world's languages"; thus, it can graphically represent dead languages or those without orthography. At its launch, the IPA contained about a hundred symbols aimed at making "available a set of phonetic symbols which would be given different articulatory values, if necessary, in different languages" (The IPA, 1999, p. 195). Initially, it had symbols for English, French, German, and other languages with unique sounds. However, modifications occur over time. Crystal (2010, p. 161) notes that "the changes in symbol reflect different interpretations by the authors of the relationships between the sounds".

The IPA symbols include:

- i. Phonemes representing sounds and diacritical marks indicating tone, aspiration, stress, and other suprasegmental features.
- ii. Non-phonemic symbols—i, u, h, ?, . (Roach, 2009, p. 10)—marking prosody, hesitation, or other speech patterns.
- iii. Notation markers—slant strokes and square brackets—serving as delimiters for phonemic (broad) and phonetic (narrow) transcriptions.
- iv. Ligature symbols, including the tie bar (¯), as in $\bar{g}b$ in 'agbada' or 'Igbo'; affricate ligature (͡), as in $\bar{t}ʃ$ in 'church'; and underscore ligature (͘), as in \bar{l} (non-syllabic /l/) in ['æ̣ṭḷ] and \bar{r} (non-rhotic /r/) in ['pɑ:̣ṛ].

Importantly, "the IPA does not provide symbols to indicate information such as spoken rapidly by a deep, hoarse, male voice" (The IPA, 1999, p. 4). Since written descriptions alone may not fully convey phonetic categories, the IPA (1999) advises that "anyone intending to use the symbols should receive training in order to learn how to produce and recognize the corresponding sounds with a reasonable degree of accuracy".

Given the IPA's efficiency in representing pronunciation, dictionaries apply it according to their lexicographic objectives and audience. As languages and dialects vary, so do phonetic transcriptions of similar words across English dialects. Each English dialect has its own set of IPA symbols, subject to periodic modification. For instance, Received Pronunciation, considered the most prestigious English accent, uses 44 IPA phonemes for transcription. This is presumably known to English teachers and learners. Recognizing each lexicographic project's right to analyze sound properties as it chooses, the IPA (1999, p. 30) affirms that it does not provide "a single 'correct' transcription, but rather the resources to express any analysis so that it is widely understood".

Teaching English Speech Sounds in the 21st Century

The importance of English in today's world keeps growing. Not only language enthusiasts but also people seeking a broader audience or following are striving to improve their English proficiency. As Cruttenden (2014, p. 325) observes, "because of the pride of place given to grammar... there has been a tendency to place less and less importance on the teaching of pronunciation."

While grammar may be prioritized, pronunciation still plays a crucial role in conveying meaning and enhancing a speaker's social image. Carley et al. (2018, pp. 32–33) note, “even if people can understand what you are saying, an off-target pronunciation may still sound comical, irritating or distracting to listeners.”

Mastering pronunciation has its advantages, and where there are learners, there are teachers. Jones (1922, p. iii) emphasizes that “no adult foreigner is likely to acquire a really good pronunciation of the English language unless he makes a scientific study of the English speech-sounds and their distribution in connected speech.” Long before English expanded widely in the 20th century, Received Pronunciation (RP) was the accepted standard. However, as English evolved and became more inclusive, pronunciation moved beyond RP. Cruttenden (2014, p. 78) states, “in the latter half of the twentieth century the type of pronunciation represented as RP changed considerably... So we get a modern type of pronunciation used by a wider range of people and specifically called 'Modern RP' by some writers.” Lindsey (2019, p. vii) affirms that “contemporary standard British speech differs from the British upper class accent of the last century, Received Pronunciation (RP)”. Modern RP, also known as General British, is used not just in England but also in parts of Wales and Scotland.

Even enthusiastic learners can feel overwhelmed by the constant changes in English, though every user contributes equally to its growth. This dynamic interaction between users and the language itself prompts continuous updates from those who document and describe it. However, lexicographers revise their work based on current usage, from pronunciation to spelling. Many schools in non-native English contexts still teach RP-based pronunciation, but native speakers themselves now see RP as outdated. Though English has grown beyond native speakers' full control, they still play a vital role in maintaining it—without them, the language could risk the fate of Latin and other lost tongues.

MacMahon (1998, p. 395) notes, “since the late twentieth century, Received Pronunciation has been gradually lessening in social prestige, and is no longer used by many members of the social and professional groups with which it was traditionally associated.” Lindsey (2019, p. v) adds, “the existing descriptions of standard British English pronunciation, known as RP, are outdated. People who speak like me now sound old-fashioned.” Cruttenden (2014, p. xvii) reinforces this, saying “many, particularly in the media, have persisted in presenting an image of RP as outdated and becoming even more than ever the speech only of the 'posh' few in the south-east of England.”

These changes didn't catch users off guard; language change is often gradual. In English pronunciation, most of the changes are mild updates to older patterns. Dictionaries adapt, so phonetic transcriptions in older editions differ from modern ones. Carley et al. (2018, p. 37) recommend replacing /e/, /æ/, and /eə/ with /ɛ/, /a/, and /ɛ:/ for a more accurate reflection of current British English. Still, Lindsey (2019, p. vii) remarks, “around the world, knowledge of British pronunciation is still rooted in RP.”

Dictionaries follow specific transcription systems, shaped by their aims, users, and the language's state. As Carley et al. (2018, p. 38) explain, “different writers use different symbols to represent the...phonemes of English. This is partly because writers have different personal preferences... It has consequently become necessary to adapt the symbols to fit in better with present-day pronunciation.” The Oxford English Dictionary (n.d.) notes, “in deciding what information is most useful to OED users, we are not limited to IPA symbols or conventions and can adapt them as needed.” Leicester (2020) encourages learners not to be discouraged by unexpected transcription differences but to consider their purpose and meaning.

Teachers must choose what and how to teach based on learners' needs. Cruttenden (2014, p. 326) advises, “teachers must not avoid using some model of pronunciation and explicitly teaching towards it, but this model should be within reach of at least some members of their class.” As pronunciation naturally evolves, teachers must keep up to support dedicated students. Using outdated IPA systems makes it hard to teach sounds, especially when students encounter varying transcriptions across dictionaries. Cruttenden (2014, p. 325) stresses that “decisions about priorities in pronunciation... are probably more acute in pronunciation teaching than in other areas.” Teaching outdated IPA can confuse and discourage learners when they meet native speakers. Lindsey (2019, p. viii) reveals, “I'm sometimes told by non-native users of English that their native speaker friends find their pronunciation old-fashioned: generally speaking, this is because they were taught RP”. Hence, teachers' choices and guidance are crucial for helping learners master English sounds.

Empirical Review

Studies on teaching or learning English as a non-native language are well investigated, and this study adds to that body of work, but what highlights the significance of this study is the specific research gap it addresses. The most relevant literature on English teaching and learning in non-native contexts is reviewed as follows:

Adedeji and Anyagwa (2022) investigated the teaching of English pronunciation in non-native settings, emphasizing the need to reconsider current methods. The study notes that while aiming for native speaker competence and performance has long been the goal for non-native speakers' pronunciation, the method of teaching has relied heavily on the native-speaker model. Although this pedagogical approach mimics the native speakers' sociolinguistic environment and “there has been continued insistence on native-like performance targets in the NNS pronunciation classroom” (p. 137), the desired competence has largely remained out of reach. The study revealed that some sampled native speaker speech was found to be unintelligible, raising questions about why non-natives continue to target native speaker performance. It concluded that political and economic motivations underlie this dependence and suggests that, for better pronunciation intelligibility both within and across countries, “an expanded and more inclusive teaching programme which takes sufficient cognisance of the learner's environmental context and

accent must be adopted” (p. 144). Consequently, ESL and EFL teachers are encouraged to reexamine their strategies and consider a more suitable and effective pronunciation curriculum.

Ndububa (2025) investigated the errors in phonological and lexical entries in the 10th edition of the Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary. Using Tarp and Bergenholtz’s (2003) Communicative Lexicography, he examined “the level of phonological precision in the OALD” and “the categories of lexical errors observable in the OALD” (p. 54). With a stratified dataset, he qualitatively and comparatively analysed entries from the print, mobile, and online versions of the dictionary, discovering that some phonological and lexical errors result from lexicographic oversight rather than the linguist’s. He also found that “some grammatical information in the OALD is misleading as it does not reflect common English usage” (p. 65). He affirms that the OALD, following the findings, does not prove to be flawless, and it is unclear whether any other lexicographic work is. Ndububa concluded that, despite its scholarly stature, the OALD has flaws that suggest some negligence, which, according to him, should not be pardoned “simply because they appear in such a prestigious dictionary” (p. 66).

Both reviewed works touched on aspects of this study, but in different and incomplete ways—creating a gap this work addresses. The first focused on methods of teaching English pronunciation to achieve native-like competence, while the second pointed out flaws in a major British learner’s dictionary that hinder users from mastering phonological representations and pronunciation. The former did not consider using dictionaries for teaching pronunciation in non-native settings, and the latter overlooked other British dictionaries and gave little attention to the pedagogical challenges involved. This study fills those gaps by examining how notable British dictionaries complicate the teaching of correct English pronunciation to non-native speakers.

Theoretical Framework

This study is primarily framed within Sweller’s (1988) Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), which posits that learning is most effective when instruction does not overload the working memory but facilitates the development of schemas. As Paas et al. (2004, p. 7) note, CLT compares learning conditions not just by performance but also by the mental effort involved. Similarly, Sweller et al. (1998, p. 266) emphasize that cognitive load has both task-based (mental load) and learner-based (mental effort) dimensions, both of which influence performance. Since learning pronunciation from phonetic transcriptions requires cognitive effort—particularly for learners unfamiliar with IPA symbols or certain transcriptions—this theory aligns well with the study’s focus on the challenges of teaching English speech sounds to non-native learners. According to Sweller et al. (1998, p. 259), “curriculum materials can differ substantially in the extent to which they impose a working memory load”. Therefore, as Uzun (2022, p. 436) points out, “a crucial factor to be considered in instruction is the level of the expertise in a given group of learners”. This principle applies to teachers who design pedagogical methods and lexicographers who create dictionaries for specific users. Sweller et al. (1998, p. 251) conclude that CLT offers guidelines for presenting information in ways that promote learner activities and optimize performance.

This study is also grounded in Lado’s (1957) Contrastive Analysis Theory (CAT), which suggests that comparing two languages reveals differences that aid second language learning. CAT asserts that learners find it easier to learn a language with similarities to their own but face challenges when the target language differs. As Lado (1957, p. 2) notes: a student learning a foreign language finds similar elements easy and different ones difficult. CAT also highlights how comparing two languages exposes weaknesses in learning materials. Being “most predictive at the phonological level” (Al-khresheh, 2016, p. 335), it supports all three objectives of this study. CAT helps explain why some English speech sounds differ from a learner’s native phonological system. Gass and Larry (2001, p. 72) note that contrastive analysis “isolates what needs to be learnt and what does not need to be learnt in an SLL situation”. Lado (1957, p. 1), quoting Fries, adds that the most effective materials are based on a scientific comparison of the target language and the learner’s native language. Despite criticism, current research has revived interest in CAT as an essential part of the theory of Second Language Acquisition. According to Al-khresheh (2016, p. 330), CAT has emerged as “one of the most significant studies ever made in describing systems of languages”.

While these two theories complement each other, comparison is a mutual feature of both. CLT compares helpful and harmful practices based on their impact on a learner’s cognitive processes. It also compares intrinsic and extraneous loads in instruction to ensure the learner is not overloaded. In mastering pronunciation using dictionary transcriptions, intrinsic loads include unfamiliar phonemes or those difficult to render, while extraneous loads are wrongly transcribed sounds, possibly with incorrect stress or prosody. CLT’s load comparison aims to reduce extraneous load while managing intrinsic load based on the learner’s level. CAT, on the other hand, compares the learner’s first language and the target language to identify mutual elements. According to CAT, mutual elements are easily comprehended and pose no load to the learner’s cognitive processes within the CLT framework, while unfamiliar elements in the target language are difficult to grasp and overload the learner’s working memory. A fusion of these two theories best addresses the research objectives.

METHODOLOGY

This study follows a comparative qualitative research design. As Creswell and Poth (2017, p. 100) note, “we conduct qualitative research because a problem or issue needs to be explored”. This design, according to Ndububa and Ugoala (2025, p. 4) “involves systematically collecting and analyzing real-world materials that capture both routine and complex situations”. A comparative approach is adopted to gain a clearer understanding of the issue and communicate findings effectively. The design encourages

persuasive writing that allows the reader to feel present in the research setting. In line with the Contrastive Analysis Theory, comparisons are made to better understand relationships, as Shahrokh and Miri (2019) explain: “comparisons are regularly drawn between various texts or manuscripts, ideas, rituals, objects, etc., especially for exploring and evaluating relations between the comparands”. Bordens and Abbott (2011, p. 102) stress that “the decisions you make at this stage of the research process do much to determine the quality of the conclusions you can draw”. Grounded in Cognitive Load Theory, this study uses a straightforward descriptive method to avoid overwhelming the reader with excessive information.

The dataset is purposively selected and stratified based on interpretive themes. It comprises 27 screenshots from the mobile and online versions of selected dictionaries, with print editions excluded for being less current. When the image on the screen is necessary and clearer observation is needed, it is zoomed. These screenshots are cropped to remove personal or irrelevant details but are not altered in any way that could misrepresent the content or introduce bias. As Nielsen (2018, p. 86) cautions, such edits should not result in “improbable, unrealistic or wrong statements that distort a fair presentation of the dictionary”. No personal bias is allowed to influence data selection or interpretation. Analysis is conducted objectively to help readers form informed opinions and to support further research. In keeping with Nielsen’s (2018, p. 87) view, reviews must remain “neutral in the sense that they should contain all material and relevant aspects regardless whether they affect the reviewers’ assessments positively or negatively”.

DATA ANALYSIS

The Orthographic Framing of Phonemes

Data in this section shows how the selected British dictionaries enclose phonemes when giving transcriptions.

Image 1. ODE — study

Image 2. LDOCE — study

Image 3. OALD — study

The above image data shows mobile screenshots of notable British dictionaries displaying phonemic transcriptions for ‘study’. In image 1, the Oxford Dictionary of English (ODE) uses vertical strokes (|) to enclose its transcription, a style used throughout the dictionary. In image 2, the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English uses round brackets (‘) for phonemic enclosure, consistently. In image 3, the Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary encloses phonemes with slant strokes (/). The first and second images go against the assertion which, according to the IPA (1999, p. 27), is that “conventionally... symbols for the phonemes of a language are placed within oblique lines”.

Phonemic Representations of a Closing Diphthong

Image 4. OED — buy

Image 5. ODE — buy

Image 6. OALD — buy

In image 4, the Oxford English Dictionary transcribes 'buy' as /bʌɪ/, showing a different representation of the usual closing diphthong /aɪ/. Image 5, a screenshot of Oxford Dictionary of English, also displays the same transcription. However, the OALD in image 6 uses the RP or old IPA transcription for 'buy' as /baɪ/. The phonemic representations in images 4 and 5 seem to reflect a particular speech variety rather than mistakes, as both dictionaries consistently use the same diphthong without substituting it for the one in image 6.

Representing the Open-mid Central Unrounded Vowel

Some British dictionaries do not transcribe the open-mid central unrounded vowel the same way. Below are the results from six notable British dictionaries for comparison.

Image 7. CD+ — bird

Image 8. LDOCE — bird

Image 9. OALD — bird

Image 10. CD — bird

Image 11. OED — bird

Image 12. ODE — bird

In the images above, the phonemic transcriptions of 'bird' are shown. While some dictionaries present the same transcription, others differ. Image 7 shows Cambridge Dictionary's version; image 8, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English; and image 9, the OALD. These three dictionaries share the same British transcription: /bɜːd/, highlighting the nucleus as an open-mid central unrounded vowel.

The next horizontal set features varying transcriptions. Image 11 is a screenshot from Collins Dictionary, showing /bɜːɹd/—a dialectal form, not representative of RP or General British, since the 'ɹ' is not pronounced in non-rhotic British accents. Image 11 displays the Oxford English Dictionary's transcription, and image 12 shows that of the Oxford Dictionary of English. Both use /ɜː/—a schwa with a length mark. This is a newer representation and suggests a dialectal variation, even though it sounds similar to the other forms in this section.

Divergent Representations of Identical Lemmas

It's not a new idea that dictionaries have peculiar ways of making entries, especially in phonemic transcriptions. Sometimes, a schwa is added or omitted, a different stress pattern is used, or other suprasegmental features are altered. In this section—unlike the previous ones where novel phonemic combinations appeared—common phonemes are used, but in new ways. The six images below reveal this.

Image 13. CD+ — strength

Image 14. OALD — strength

Image 15. OED — strength

Image 16. LDOCE — oppor...

Image 17. OED — opport...

Image 18. CD — opportunity

Here are key points on teaching English speech sounds to non-natives using lexicographic phonemic transcriptions, which also contributes to students' difficulty in Spoken English exams. In image 13, Cambridge Dictionary transcribes strength as /strenθ/, while image 14 from OALD shows /strenkθ/, adding /k/ in the phonemic environment. Image 15 from the Oxford English Dictionary shows free variations: /stren(k)θ/, where /k/ is optional, and /strenθ/, matching image 13.

Dictionaries also differ in transcribing opportunity across images 16 to 18. In image 16, Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English gives /ɒpə'tju:nəti/, while image 17 from the Oxford English Dictionary shows /ɒpə'tju:nəti/, replacing the second schwa /ə/ with /ɪ/—a seeming allophone of /ɪ/—and another variant /ɒpə'tju:nəti/, using /tʃ/ in place of /tj/. Image 18 from Collins Dictionary shows /ɒpə'tju:nəti/, similar to image 16 but includes an /r/, indicating an allophone of /r/ is produced in pronunciation. In this transcription too, two vowels are underlined, each within a stressed syllable. It appears that LDOCE uses underlining in place of the traditional IPA primary stress mark (ˈ) to indicate stress.

Inconsistencies in the OALD's Phonemic System

Ndububa (2025, pp. 61–62) highlighted inconsistencies in the transcription of repeated dialectal entries and in pronunciation representation based on word origin in the OALD. Here, other irregularities and errors in its phonemic representations are shown as follows:

Image 19. Henry VIII

Image 20. Wisden

Image 21. Drachma

Image 22. The Commons

Image 23. R A (Rab) Butler

Image 24. (The) Yukon

Image 19 shows the offline mobile version of the OALD with an incorrect transcription of ‘Henry VIII’. It gives /ˈhenri ɪtʃ/, which actually means ‘Henry The H’. The correct transcription, also found in the online version, is /ˈhenri ɪtʃθ/.

In Image 20, the audio icons are misplaced. Normally, each icon should align with a transcription so users can hear the pronunciation of the word beside it—a useful feature for learning speech sounds. But here, the four icons are wrongly placed, leaving the last transcription without one. This is misleading and reflects poor lexicographic attention.

Image 21 shows a similar issue. Two plurals of ‘drachma’ are listed, but only one transcription is provided, leaving the user to guess which applies to which.

In Image 22, the transcription is incomplete. The determiner in the headword is omitted, which might confuse learners about whether it should be pronounced. The transcription given is /ˈkɒmənz/, but the full version should be /ðə ˈkɒmənz/.

Image 23 reveals another inconsistency. *R. A. ('Rab') Butler* is transcribed as /ˈræb ˈbʌtlə(r)/, ignoring the initials ‘R’ and ‘A’. This could mislead users into thinking that the OALD or dictionaries in general do not transcribe initials.

Finally, Image 24 highlights further inconsistency. Ndububa (2025, p. 65) confirms that both the offline and online versions of the OALD typically omit transcription for ‘the’ when it appears in brackets. But in this image, a lemma beginning with ‘the’ is fully transcribed, unlike the incomplete ones shown in Images 22 and 23, contradicting the dictionary’s own pattern.

Multiple Interpretations of the Schwa and Unstressed Vowel Sounds Across Dictionaries

A natural English sentence has many weakened syllables, meaning vowels that are clear when spoken alone become weakened in normal speech. Some phonologists classify all weak sounds as schwas, while others do not. This section examines how different British dictionaries depict and understand the schwa and other unstressed vowel sounds.

Image 25. CD+ — Muha... Image 26. OED — Muha... Image 27. LDOCE — Muha...

In image 25, Cambridge Dictionary transcribes 'Muhammad' as /mə'hæm.ɪd/, showing that the 'u' is a schwa, the first 'a' is stressed with an /æ/ sound, and the second 'a' gives an /ɪ/ sound in the final syllable. In image 26, Oxford English Dictionary renders it as /mə'hæmɪd/: the 'u' gives a weak /ʊ/ sound, the stressed syllable has a modern /a/ for /æ/, and the final vowel, though written as 'a', is a weak /ɪ/ indicated by the slashed phoneme /ɪ/. This shows weak vowels in both the first and last syllables. Image 27 offers almost the same transcription as image 25 but clearly marks the final syllable as a schwa /ə/, resulting in /mʊ'hæməd/. These variations create cognitive load for students struggling to decide which version to adopt. Here, teacher guidance is essential, though the challenge of choosing and teaching the appropriate form remains.

Findings

In the just concluded data presentation and discussion, it was found that many notable British dictionaries have dissimilar ways of enclosing phonemic transcriptions. These are dictionaries that influence users and the teaching and learning of English. The OED uses vertical strokes, LDOCE uses round brackets, while the OALD uses slant strokes. The study also found that in addition to Carley et al.'s (2018, p. 37) new vowels, some British dictionaries have other new phonemes in their vowel systems. Thus, instead of the regular diphthong /aɪ/ used in OALD and Cambridge Dictionary, the OED and the ODE use /aɪ/ as their equivalent. Findings also revealed that the open-mid central unrounded vowel commonly marked as /ɜ:/ is perceived differently by some of the biggest British dictionaries. The OED and the ODE mark it as /ɜ:/, a phonological rendition similar to a long schwa sound. LDOCE indicates that the sound is rhotic, which is not a phonological feature of RP and suggests consideration for a variety of English pronunciation systems.

As shown in images 13 to 15, some British dictionaries add a /k/ sound in pronouncing 'strength', others do not, while some state that it is optional. In images 16 to 18 and 25 to 27, it was found that dictionaries have distinct ideas of the schwa and unstressed syllables — this, English teachers and learners must understand. The OALD, as shown in images 19 and 20, has some lexicographic errors. Formatting can be disrupted or distorted, resulting in erroneous transcriptions. There is a perceived inconsistency in British dictionaries' style of rendering transcriptions. The OALD, for instance, in its digital versions, does not transcribe the bracketed indefinite article 'the' in the initial parts of lemmas but was found to transcribe 'the' in a compound lemma — a violation of its own rule. It was also found to avoid transcribing 'the' in another word where the article is not bracketed. Finally, prosody is marked differently by British dictionaries: in Collins Dictionary (online), vowel phonemes are underlined to mark stress placement — there is no way of distinguishing the primary from the secondary stress — while the OED strikes a line through an unstressed vowel.

Conclusion

In line with the first objective of this study—to examine how British dictionaries present phonetic transcriptions and pronunciation guidance for non-native learners using the Contrastive Analysis Theory (CAT)—it was observed that these dictionaries serve different lexicographic purposes and target specific users. Therefore, some of their outputs are not errors but intentional features. Teachers, applying CAT alongside the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) to avoid overloading students' working memories, should choose dictionaries that suit their class. They should also learn not only the objectives of their selected dictionaries but review the pronunciation guides. Further training and attention to dictionary use are also advised.

For the second objective—analyzing the effectiveness of British dictionaries in helping non-native speakers acquire accurate pronunciation—it was found that these dictionaries are valuable pedagogical tools. However, teachers must recognize that their uses and aims differ, so reviewing dictionary content carefully is important.

Regarding the third objective—identifying the challenges non-native English speakers face when learning speech sounds using British dictionaries—it was found that unfamiliarity with a dictionary's purpose and style hinders progress. While consulting multiple dictionaries can broaden learning, it can be confusing if learners do not understand the principles behind each one.

Independent learners who understand the aims of the dictionaries they use are better able to judge what is accurate. The comparative approach of CLT also helps in selecting suitable dictionaries to prevent cognitive overload.

Finally, CAT shows that avoiding any particular dictionary altogether could mean missing out on its useful features. Learning English speech sounds through British dictionaries can be effective, but teachers and learners must remember that “there can be many systems of phonemic transcription for the same variety of a language, all of which conform fully to the principles of the IPA. Sometimes the differences between the systems result from the fact that more than one phonetic symbol may be appropriate for a phoneme” (IPA, 1999, p. 30). With this in mind, using multiple dictionaries can expose learners to free variations in pronunciation, though accommodating these differences while maintaining a consistent learning target can be challenging.

Recommendation

The researcher further recommends that dictionary makers maintain consistency in lexicographic entries to reduce cognitive load on teachers and learners. For further studies, since the novel phonemes treated here are vowels, prospective researchers may explore novel consonants and how these or other dictionaries handle free variations. American transcriptions were not examined in this study; further studies may consider them.

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